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Review Article

MATERNAL PERCEPTION OF THE EFFECTS OF INSOMNIA DURING PREGNANCY ON THE FETAL OUTCOMES IN THE EASTERN PROVINCE OF SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract:

Insomnia during pregnancy become a major public health problem because of its detrimental effects on maternal and fetal outcomes. Therefore, the aim of the study is to conduct a study in the eastern province of Saudi Arabia to explore insomnia experienced by pregnant women and to investigate the complications of insomnia on the maternal status as well as fetal outcomes.

***Methods:** a cross sectional study will be conducted among 283 women. Data will be collected through electronic questionnaires that will be filled by participants. The Expected results of this study will indicate if there is a statistically significant difference between insomnia during pregnancy among smokers and non- smokers women and adverse maternal and fetal outcomes. In conclusion, the findings may help to raise the awareness of the adverse effects of insomnia during pregnancy in maternal and fetal outcomes.*

***Results:** The knowledge score regarding the effects of insomnia during pregnancy among mothers, it showed that 18.4% have poor knowledge, 53.4% have moderate knowledge, 26.6% have good knowledge and 1.6% have Excellent Knowledge.*

***Conclusion:** The majority of the respondents have moderate knowledge regarding the effects of insomnia during pregnancy on the fatal outcomes. The findings may help to increase the awareness of the effects of insomnia on the fetal outcomes.*

***Keywords:** Pregnancy, Sleep, Insomnia, Outcomes, fetal.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Sleep is a physiological need for all human being, along with the food, water and oxygen. The amount of night time sleep is a vital indicator of overall mental health, physical health, quality of life, and safety. So, getting sufficient sleep per day will improve the cognitive functions, alertness, memory, performance and improving the validity of the immune system. Even though the recommended daily sleep vary by age and gender, the National Sleep Foundation has recommended daily 7 to 8 hours of sleep for adults [1].

Sleep problems are characterized by either, difficulty falling asleep, difficulty staying asleep during the night, excessive daytime sleepiness, snoring during sleep or sleep walking ,so if there are prolonged periods of wakefulness during the sleep period or difficult falling asleep during the sleep period this termed as insomnia [2]. In addition, insomnia can be define specifically according to the International Classification of Sleep Disorders (ICSD-2), the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) and the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM-5). According to the (ICSD-2) insomnia is defined as subjective report of difficulty initiating or maintaining sleeping, waking up too early or subjective feeling of unrefreshed after sleeping despite the presence of sufficient circumstances to sleep causing daytime impairment. According to (DSM-5) and (ICD-10) insomnia is defined as difficulty falling, maintaining or initiating the sleep and short sleep duration [18].

Insomnia can be caused by many factors related to age, medications, diet, smoking, environmental factor such as shift work, and one of the prominent factor that can lead to insomnia is the changes that occur during some period of your life particularly during pregnancy [3]. During pregnancy, the total daytime sleepiness and sleep time increase during the first trimester, in contrast during the third trimester, the total daytime sleepiness and sleep time will decrees [7]. The National Sleep Foundation has reported that about 79% of women reported that their sleep has been altered during pregnancy more than any other time in their lives. Sleep problem during pregnancy is usually

caused by the hormonal changes, lower back pain, urinary frequency, snoring and disturbed sleeping position. Pregnant women particularly need to get sufficient sleep in order to nourish the development of their infants and the energy they need for the labor and delivery process [3].

Likewise, pregnancy is a stressful period since it is associated with physiological, psychological and social changes that can significantly affect the quality of sleep and wellness. Insomnia during pregnancy is associated with risk factors. A study has indicated that the common risk factors for insomnia in general population are low income level, living alone, low self-perceived societal status, minority ethnicity, urban environment and long work hours [4]. Insomnia during pregnancy is very common thought to affect up to 75% of pregnant women at some point during the pregnancy [5]. In addition, insomnia has become a major public health concern in Saudi Arabia in the last few years. A recent study on Sleepless in Makkah City, Saudi Arabia, reported that the relevance of insomnia was 29.4%, and females were twice as likely as male to complain of insomnia [6].

Chronic sleep deprivation has significant effects on the glucose and fat metabolism, job performance, inflammatory process, cognitive, mental and learning functions. Moreover, 4-8 hours of sleep restriction will increase the inflammatory markers especially interleukin-1 (IL-1), IL-2, IL-6, tumor necrosis factor (TNF) α , and C-reactive protein, and that will cause significant decline on the functions of the immune system. In addition, several studies have demonstrated that prolonged sleep restriction usually less than 6 hours will increase the risk of mortality by 26% in men and 21% in women. Similarly, prolonged period of sleep usually more than 9 hours will increase the risk of mortality by 24% in men and 17% in women [7].

Besides deteriorating of the quality and quantity of sleep during pregnancy, several authors have demonstrated that insomnia during pregnancy can adversely affect the health of the pregnant women, and

increase the risk of adverse maternal and fetal outcomes [7].

Author has examined Maternal Sleep and Fetal Outcome demonstrates that insomnia during pregnancy can lead to prematurity which it is one of the major public health issues that significantly increases the risk of infant morbidity and mortality. In a recent study from Greece has reported that women with sleep restriction less than 5 hours of sleep at the third trimester are associated with high risk of preterm births [8].

Preterm birth is defined as infant born before 37 weeks of gestation. Beside insomnia during pregnancy, there are other several risk factors for preterm labor and delivery such as cigarette smoking, cardiopulmonary disease, diabetes mellitus, hyperthyroidism, hypertension, gestational bleeding, intrauterine infection, cervical or uterine anomalies, low birth weight, multiple gestation, low socioeconomic status, black race and low or high maternal age. Preterm birth

increases the risk of infant mortality by 75% and long term morbidity in more than half of the infants. Furthermore, preterm birth increases the risk of postpartum depression since the premature babies will take time to sleep through the night compared to the mature babies and this will disturb maternal sleep leading to the postpartum depression [7]

Regarding the relation between insomnia during pregnancy and preterm birth, a study showed that sleep restriction during the mid and late pregnancy will increase the serum level of pro-inflammatory cytokine (IL-6), which plays a role in initiating spontaneous preterm labor and delivery. Also, the elevation of serum cytokine will stimulate the production of prostaglandin that will induce uterine contraction and lead to the preterm birth. However, more studies are needed to determine whether insomnia is determinant cause of preterm labor and delivery and the specific mechanism associated with it [7]. Source of this picture

Table 1

Risk factors for preterm delivery

Category	Risk factors
Sociodemographic characteristics	Low and high maternal age, Black race, single marital status, low socioeconomic status
Psychological factors	Higher levels of psychological or social stress, depression, anxiety
Obstetric history and pregnancy characteristics	Short interpregnancy interval (< 6 months), Prior history of preterm birth or low birth weight, multiple second trimester spontaneous abortions, in vitro fertilization pregnancy, multiple gestations, low prepregnancy body-mass index
Medical complications of pregnancy	Placental abnormalities, gestational bleeding, cervical and uterine anomalies, intrauterine infection
Chronic disorders	Cardiopulmonary disease, diabetes mellitus, asthma, hyperthyroidism, epilepsy, hypertension
Substance use and abuse	Cigarette smoking

A review on the Relationship between Sleep Deprivation during Pregnancy and Maternal and Fetal Outcomes, discovered that women averaging less than 6 hours of nighttime sleep during the last months of pregnancy are potentially at higher risk of cesarean births than the women who are getting more than 6 hours of sleep [9]. Researchers have also investigated that pregnant women who suffers from insomnia during pregnancy are more likely to experience longer labor, and complain of pain and discomfort during labor than the women who are getting adequate amount of sleep [10].

Likewise, it is well understood that women experience sleep restriction during pregnancy as well as in the postpartum period since there is great change in woman's life, and the new-born baby requires attention and will disturb maternal sleep in the first months after delivery [11]. Hence, insomnia can potentially increase the risk of depression in the prenatal period, and insomnia may precede to cause postpartum depression. A review of 21 longitudinal studies found that women with insomnia during pregnancy had a twofold risk of developing depression, and even after recovery from depression there is an increased risk of relapse [12]. Cross-sectional study has reported insomnia and depression are conditions associated with each other before and after delivery [13,14]. Furthermore, maternal depression before and after deliver has a critical impact on infant's emotional and cognitive functions [15,16].

Postpartum depression is one of the most common complication during the postpartum period, and it is usually due to the change of on the woman's life, stress faced on work and social activities, and the demand require for the infant's care. Postpartum depression refers to depression that occurs within 4 weeks after delivery and lasts up to 6 months. The symptoms of the postpartum depression are characterized by episodes of persistent low mood, loss interest on the activities that were enjoyed before, change on the appetite or weight, feeling worthlessness or guilty, insomnia or hypersomnia, loss of energy or fatigue, physical retardation or agitation, inability to concentrate and thought of death or suicidal ideas. Postpartum depression may also include other symptoms such as inability to sleep when the baby sleeps, concerns about hurting the baby and having the feeling of inadequate maternal role. Postpartum depression differ from postpartum blue in which the later one is defined as mild form of depression with a duration of 3-7 days [7].

Beside insomnia during pregnancy, there are several risk factors that increase the risk of postpartum depression such as low socioeconomic status, social isolation, cesarean delivery, preterm birth, low self-esteem and stressful life events. The suggested mechanism of postpartum depression is the high level of progesterin and estrogen during pregnancy and then the sudden fall of these hormones during the first postpartum days lead to the postpartum depression [7].

Table 2

Risk factors for postpartum depression

Category	Risk factors
Socioeconomic characteristics	Low socioeconomic status, limited educational attainment, single marital status, poor marital relationship, social isolation, low levels of social support
Obstetrical factors	Unplanned/unwanted pregnancy, cesarean section delivery, preterm delivery
Psychiatric and psychosocial factors	Low self-esteem, psychological distress, childcare stress, history of previous depression or postpartum depression, anxiety or depression during pregnancy, experiencing stressful life event during pregnancy

Regarding the relation between insomnia during pregnancy and postpartum depression, sleep restriction during pregnancy cause the elevation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 (IL-1), IL-2, IL-6, tumor necrosis factor (TNF) α , and C-reactive protein that contribute to the development of postpartum depression and this is the suggested mechanism that lead to postpartum depression in women who experience insomnia during pregnancy [7].

Moreover, poor sleep has a critical impact in pregnant women, potentially leading to maternal complications such as hypertension, preeclampsia and gestational diabetes [17].

Speaking about the Pharmacology management of insomnia during pregnancy, there are several medications that are effective in the management of insomnia such as benzodiazepine-receptor agonists,

melatonin and variants, antidepressants, antipsychotics and antihistamines. Benzodiazepine such as temazepam and zopiclone are known as hypnotic drugs. These drugs act on gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptor, specifically GABA_A receptors that are involved in falling and maintaining of sleep in the non-rapid eye movement (non-REM) sleep and REM sleep which will help in regulating the sleep [18].

However, some of the sleep medications cause serious effects on the fetus. According to several studies done on pregnant women, only one out of five categories of sleep medications has been found to be safe during pregnancy and has no effects on the fetus development. This category of medications include diphenhydramine, zolpidem, sertraline, meperidine, oxymorphone, caffeine and pemoline. However, most of pregnant women prefer to avoid using sleep medications during pregnancy [18].

Table 1—Pregnancy Safety Classification for Commonly Used Medications for Sleep Disorders

DRUG	Drug Class	Pregnancy Category*	COMMENTS ^{51,52}
<u>Insomnia</u>			
Diphenhydramine	Antihistamine	B	No evidence of fetal harm in animal studies
Zolpidem	Imidazopyridine	B	No evidence of fetal harm in animal studies
Amitriptyline	Tricyclic antidepressant	C	Animal teratogen at high doses, insufficient human data
Doxepin	Tricyclic antidepressant	C	Possible association with major birth defects, polydactyly
Trazedone	Antidepressant	C	Fetal toxicity & teratogenicity in animals at high doses
Zaleplon	Pyrazolopyrimidine	C	Increased stillbirths in animal studies, insufficient human data
Lorazepam	Benzodiazepine	D	“Floppy infant syndrome,” respiratory depression, possible association with anal atresia
Estazolam	Benzodiazepine	X	May have adverse effects similar to other benzodiazepines
Flurazepam	Benzodiazepine	X	No reported major adverse effects in animals or humans, but known adverse effects of other benzodiazepines
Quazepam	Benzodiazepine	X	May have adverse effects similar to other benzodiazepines
Temazepam	Benzodiazepine	X	Potential interaction with diphenhydramine, causing stillbirth in animals and 1 human case
Triazolam	Benzodiazepine	X	May have adverse effects similar to other benzodiazepines

Regarding the non-pharmacology management of insomnia during pregnancy, several studies demonstrate that non-pharmacology treatment is effective in treating insomnia during pregnancy and it includes cognitive behavioral therapy, acupuncture, complementary and alternative medicine [18].

Cognitive behavioral therapy is done to correct some behaviors that will improve night time sleep. For example, cognitive behavioral therapy will correct excessive daytime caffeine intake, daytime napping

and minimizing time awake during the night. Also, cognitive behavioral therapy will promote sleep hygiene education that consists of emphasizing pre-sleep habits such as avoiding using electronic device before sleep, performing exercise or yoga, meditating, avoid eating food or drinking caffeine before the bedtime and sticking to specific bedtime and wake up schedule. Sleep restriction is another cognitive behavioral therapy approach that consists of reducing the time spent on the bed before sleeping and increase the desire to sleep therefore this will promote efficient sleep [18].

Cognitive-Behavior Therapy for Insomnia	
Session 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psychoeducation about sleep and insomnia • Introduction or review of the daily sleep diary • Sleep restriction (may be reported to Session 2)
Session 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the daily sleep diary • Stimulus control instructions
Session 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the daily sleep diary • Identification and modification of dysfunctional sleep-related beliefs and attitudes
Session 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of the daily sleep diary • Sleep hygiene instructions
Session 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of therapeutic gains and remaining challenges • Relapse prevention <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Identify risk factors (stressors) ✓ Review of CBT-I strategies

Acupuncture is a traditional Chinese therapy involves inserting fine needles to the skin. It is done to promote sleeping and managing insomnia in addition to treating other several conditions such as lower back pain, arthritis and headache. Acupuncture promote sleeping by increasing the serum level of melatonin which is usually low in pregnant women with sleeping problem, therefore it will promote sleeping. For complementary and alternative medicine, they consist of using herbs such as herbal tea, herbal supplement of lavender and valerian and essential oil which all can promote sleeping [18].

Because of the adverse effects of the pharmacology treatment of insomnia during pregnancy on the fetus, most of the doctors prefer the non-pharmacology treatment over the pharmacology. However, there are no adequate studies that support the use of either interventions according to their effectiveness and safety. So, if there were more studies it will provide better judgment for the doctors as well as the mother to decide the effective treatment of insomnia during pregnancy [18].

With this background in mind, the aim of the study is to conduct a study to demonstrate the Maternal Perception of the effects of insomnia during pregnancy on the fetal outcomes in the eastern province of Saudi Arabia, and to evaluate whether insomnia during pregnancy may predict maternal and fetal complications.

Objectives:

- 1- To explore insomnia experienced by pregnant women.
- 2- To investigate the complications of insomnia on the maternal status as well as fetal outcomes.

Study Methodology:

▪ **Study population and sample size**

The proposed systemic review and meta-Analysis study was carried out among mothers in the eastern province of Saudi Arabia. The study was conducted during July-August 2023. The study population include female in the eastern province between the age group of 18 to above 55.

The estimated sample size was 283 which was calculated using internet software for sample calculator [RaoSoft, Inc. http://www.raosoft.com/sample_size.html](http://www.raosoft.com/sample_size.html) [19], with 95% confidence interval and 5% margin error, and 50% response distribution.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

▪ **Study Procedure and Data Collection**

Data was collected using a self-administered electronic questionnaire (appendix 1). The questionnaire had been reviewed for content validity and then translated into Arabic and reliability test had been done.

The questionnaire was divided into three sections: the first section was about socio demographic data such as age, living area, smoking status, drinking coffee or tea, educational level and number of gravida. The second section consisted of questions all related to a pregnancy and sleeping status during pregnancy.

The third part consisted of true and false answers for 10 questions to test the respondent's knowledge and perception of insomnia during pregnancy its effects on the fetal outcomes.

Scoring methods for the questionnaire:

The third part of the questionnaire which was related to the knowledge had the following scoring criteria, 1 point for the correct answer and 0 point for the wrong answer and the total score out of 10 to 10 questions and the criteria was set as following groups, 1-3 poor, 4-6 moderate, 7-8 good, and 9-10 excellent knowledge.

Data Collection method;

▪ **Outcomes:**

The findings may help to raise the awareness of the adverse effects of insomnia during pregnancy in maternal and fetal outcomes.

▪ **Statistical Analysis:**

The data obtained from the study is analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program version 21. Measurable data is presented in the form of frequencies, percentages, means (X) and Standard Deviations (SD). Analytical tests that are used includes Chi-square is used for nominal data and T-test for numerical data. The significance level will be set at $p \leq 0.05$ which is considered statically significant.

▪ **Ethical Issues:**

- Ethical clearance will be obtained from college of medicine at KFU as well as the local health authorities.
- Consent will be obtained from participants with full explanation of the study with their right of accepting and refusing to participate in the questionnaire.
- Confidentiality will be maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS:

A total of 284 participants completed the questionnaire. The results are shown in Table 1, the minimum age was 18 and the maximum age was 55 and above. It demonstrates that 117 (41.3%) of the subjects were the age group 26-35, 65 (23%) of the subjects were the age group 36-45, 62 (21.9%) of the subjects were the age group 18-25, 28 (9.9%) of the subjects were the age group 46-55 and 11 (3.9%) of the subjects were the age group 55 and above. Most of the participants are living in the city 232 (82%), and 51 (18%) are living in the urban. In addition, 225 (79.5%) were non-smokers, 34 (12%) were ex-smokers and 24 (8.5%) are currently smokers. Also, 92 (32.5%) drink one cup per day of caffeine, 78 (27.6%) drink two

cups, 45 (15.9%) drink three cups, 37(13.1%) drink four and more cups and 31 (11%) do not drink caffeine. Regarding the educational status, 10 (3.5%) were not educated, 16 (5.7%) primary school, 26 (9.2%)

middle school, 56 (19.8) secondary school and 175(61.8) university. Regarding the gravida, 76 (26.9%) are one gravida, 59 (20.8%) are two gravida, 50 (17.7%) are three gravida and 98 (34.6%) are four or more gravida.

Table I: Demographic table

Variables	Frequency (%)
Age :	
18-25	62 (21.9%)
26-35	117 (41.3%)
36-45	65 (23%)
46-55	28 (9.9%)
Above55	11 (3.9%)
Living area :	
City :	232 (2%)
Urban :	51(18%)
Smoking Status:	
Not smoker	225 (79.5%)
Ex-smoker	34 (12%)
Currently smoker	24 (8.5%)
Drinking caffeine:	
Drink one cup	92 (32.5%)
two cups	78 (27.6%)
drink three cups	45 (15.9%)
drink four and more cups	37(13.1%)
Do not drink caffeine	31 (11%)
Educational status:	
Not Educated	10 (3.5%)
Primary school	16 (5.7%)
Middle school	26 (9.2%)
Secondary school	56 (19.8)
University	175(61.8)
Gravida:	
One	76 (26.9%)
Two	59 (20.8%)
Three	50 (17.7%)
four	98 (34.6%)

Table II: Illustrates maternal sleeping status during pregnancy among smokers and non-smokers mothers

Variables	Frequency		P value
	Non-Smokers	smokers	
Have you experience insomnia during pregnancy before?			0.036
Yes			
No	134(45.8%)	24 (10%)	
	101 (55.2%)	10 (5%)	
Average sleeping hours before pregnancy?			0.0001
Less than 7 hours	63 (22.3%)	131(46.3%)	
7-8 hours	23(8.1%)	11(2.9%)	
9 hours	61(30.5%)	206(54.6%)	
10 and more hours	66(23.3%)	6(1.6%)	
Average sleeping hours during pregnancy?			0.001
Less than 7 hours	105 (37.1%)	10(2.7%)	
7-8 hours	104(36.7%)	1(0.44%)	
9 hours	52(18.4%)	200(60%)	
10 and more hours	22(7.8%)	72(15%)	
Do you take afternoon nape during pregnancy?			0.042
Yes	172 (60.8%)	183 (65%)	
No	111 (39.2%)	100 (35%)	
Do you experience snoring during pregnancy?			0.043
Yes	199 (70.3%)	209(75%)	
NO	84 (29.7%)	77 (35%)	
How would you score your sleeping during pregnancy?			0.0014
Excellent	43 (15.2%)	105(37.1%)	
Very good	110 (38.9%)	22(7.8%)	
Good	101 (35.7%)	100(35.7%)	
Poor	29 (10.2%)	56(19.4)	
Have you take any sleeping medications during pregnancy?			0.003
Yes	49(17.3%)	122 (70%)	
No	234(82.7%)	161 (30%)	

Table III: Illustrates the Maternal awareness and knowledge of the effects of insomnia during pregnancy on the fetal outcomes.

Questions	<u>N. (%)</u>	P value
Q1- Insomnia during pregnancy has great effects on the fetal outcomes ?(True) correct Wrong	200 (70.7%) 83 (29.3%)	0.062
Q2 - Insomnia during pregnancy increase the risk of preterm labor and delivery? (True) correct wrong	81 (28.6%) 202 (71.4 %)	0.783
Q3-Insomnia during pregnancy increase the risk of cesarean section delivery instead of normal vaginal delivery? (true) correct wrong	75 (26.5%) 208 (73.5%)	0.714
Q4 - Insomnia during pregnancy increase the risk of postpartum depression? (true) Correct Wrong	154 (54.4%) 129 (45.6%)	0.397

Questions	<u>N. (%)</u>	P value
Q5-Have you ever been diagnosed with either gestational diabetes, preeclampsia or chronic hypertension? No Yes, gestational Diabetes Yes, Preeclampsia Yes, chronic hypertension	178 (62.9%) 44 (15.5%) 23 (8.1%) 38 (13.4%)	0.062
Q6 - Insomnia during pregnancy increase the risk of sever labor pain? (True) correct wrong	107 (37.8%) 176 (62.2%)	0.783
Q7-Insomnia during pregnancy increase the risk of cesarean section delivery instead of normal vaginal delivery? (true) correct wrong	75 (26.5%) 208 (73.5%)	0.714
Q8 - Insomnia during pregnancy increase the risk of fetal intrauterine growth restriction? (true) Correct Wrong	101 (35.7%) 182 (64.3%)	0.397
Q9 - Insomnia during pregnancy can be treated? (true) Correct Wrong	191 (67.5%) 92 (32.5%)	

TableIV: demonstrates the knowledge score regarding the effects of insomnia during pregnancy among mothers, it showed that 18.4% have poor knowledge, 53.4% have moderate knowledge, 26.6% have good knowledge and 1.6% have Excellent Knowledge.

Knowledge's scores	NO. (%)
Poor Knowledge	18.4%
Moderate Knowledge	53.4%
Good Knowledge	26.6%
Excellent Knowledge	1.6%
The mean of the knowledge	7.602564

Figure 1: shows the knowledge score of maternal perception of the effects of insomnia during pregnancy on the fetal outcomes.

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of the study is to explore insomnia experienced by pregnant women. In addition, it aims to investigate the maternal perception toward the effects and consequences of insomnia during pregnancy on the fetal outcomes in the eastern province of Saudi Arabia. The results of the study has revealed that the majority of the respondents have moderate knowledge 53.4% regarding the perception of the effects of insomnia during pregnancy on the

fetal outcomes. This study showed similar result with other study which was done by Pardo G, Goularte J and Hoefel A [20]. Overall, there was no significant difference between smokers and non-smokers. Regarding their awareness of the effects of insomnia on the fetal outcomes, only 1.6% revealed excellent perception, 26.6 revealed good knowledge while 18.4% showed poor level of perception. Most of the respondents (70.7%) are aware that insomnia have effects on the fetal outcomes, and (54.4%) of the

respondents are aware that postpartum depression is a consequence of insomnia during pregnancy.

Surprisingly, few participants were able to answer the other questions related to the effects of insomnia on the fetal outcomes such as preterm labor and delivery (28.6%), cesarean delivery (26.5%), severe labor pain (37.8%), fetal intrauterine growth restriction (35.7%), (41.3%) for the gestational diabetes, preeclampsia and chronic hypertension. Moreover, most of the respondents (67.5%) are aware that insomnia during pregnancy can be managed with pharmacology or non-pharmacology treatment. These results are similar to a study conducted by Kızıllırmak A, Timur S and Kartal B which was conducted in Turkey to explore insomnia in pregnancy and factors related to insomnia, it shows that they are aware that preterm labor (30%), gestational diabetes (32.7%) and preeclampsia (44.2%) are consequences of insomnia during pregnancy [21].

Other study which was conducted by Chang J for Sleep Deprivation during Pregnancy and Maternal and Fetal Outcomes: Is There a Relationship, it shows that 10% to 15% of childbearing women experience postpartum. Among high risk populations, the prevalence of postpartum depression can reach 40% to 50% [22]. Similar result of the present study which was conducted by Reichner C, shows that 23.7% of mothers have moderate knowledge and awareness of the effects of insomnia during pregnancy on the fetal outcomes [23].

There are some limitations of this study. The population was involved were only the women in the eastern province of Saudi Arabia . In addition, assessment the awareness of the effects of insomnia during pregnancy was through risk factors and the consequences of insomnia, so the survey encourages guessing and it may not be true reflection of the respondents' knowledge regarding the effects of insomnia.

CONCLUSION:

Insomnia during pregnancy become a major public health problem because of its detrimental effects on maternal and fetal outcomes. The majority of the respondents have moderate knowledge regarding the effects of insomnia during pregnancy on the fetal outcomes. The findings may help to increase the awareness of the effects of insomnia on the fetal outcomes.

REFERENCES:

[1] National Sleep Foundation. Let Sleep Work for You. [cited 2008 May 22].

- [2] Roth T. Insomnia: Definition, Prevalence, Etiology, and Consequences. 2007 Aug 15;3(5 Suppl): S7-10.
- [3] Chang JJ, Pien GW, Duntley SP, Macones GA. Sleep Deprivation during Pregnancy and Maternal and Fetal Outcomes: Is There a Relationship? 2010 Apr;14(2):107-14.
- [4] Kushida CA, editor. Sleep Deprivation: Basic Science, Physiology and Behavior. New York; Marcel Dekker; 2005.
- [5] Tauman R. Maternal Sleep and Fetal Outcome. 2013, 6, (Suppl 1: M8) 63-67.
- [6] Bashawri H. Sleepless in Makkah City, Saudi Arabia: Prevalence and Risk Factors of Insomnia and the Variations in Sleep Quality among Visitors of Primary Health Care Centers. 2013: 77.
- [7] Chang JJ, Pien GW, Duntley SP, Macones GA. Sleep Deprivation during Pregnancy and Maternal and Fetal Outcomes: Is There a Relationship? 2010 Apr;14(2):107-14.
- [8] Tauman R. Maternal Sleep and Fetal Outcome. 2013, 6, (Suppl 1: M8) 63-67.
- [9] Lee KA, Gay CL. Sleep in late pregnancy predicts length of labor and type of delivery. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2004;191(6):2041-6.
- [10] Chang JJ, Pien GW, Duntley SP, Macones GA. Sleep Deprivation during Pregnancy and Maternal and Fetal Outcomes: Is There a Relationship? 2010 Apr;14(2):107-14.
- [11] Insana SP, Montgomery-Downs HE (2012) Sleep and sleepiness among firsttime postpartum parents: A field- and laboratory-based multimethod assessment. Dev Psychobiol.
- [12] Baglioni C, Battagliese G, Feige B, Spiegelhalder K, Nissen C, et al. (2011). Insomnia as a predictor of depression: a meta-analytic evaluation of longitudinal epidemiological studies. J Affect Disord 135: 10–19.
- [13] Dorheim SK, Bondevik GT, Eberhard-Gran M, Bjorvatn B (2009) Sleep and depression in postpartum women: a population-based study. Sleep 32: 847–855.
- [14] Marques M, Bos S, Soares MJ, Maia B, Pereira AT, et al. (2011) Is insomnia in late pregnancy a risk factor for postpartum depression/depressive symptomatology? Psychiatry Res 186: 272–280.
- [15] Evans J, Melotti R, Heron J, Ramchandani P, Wiles N, et al. (2012) The timing of maternal depressive symptoms and child cognitive development: a longitudinal study. J Child Psychol Psychiatry 53: 632–640.
- [16] Gerardin P, Wendland J, Bodeau N, Galin A, Bialobos S, et al. (2011) Depression during pregnancy: is the developmental impact earlier in

- boys? A prospective case- control study. *J Clin Psychiatry* 72: 378–387.
- [17] Kryger, MH *et al.* "Principles and Practice of Sleep Medicine." *ExpertConsult*, 5th edition, 2011, pp. 1582-1584.
- [18] Moriichi M, Tomita N, Sado M, Ota. (2014) Interventions for insomnia during pregnancy. 22 October 2014, 56-43.
- [19] Raosoft.com.(2019).*Sample Size Calculator by Raosoft, Inc.*. [online] Available at: <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>.
- [20] Pardo G, Goularte J, Hoefel A, Castro A, Kucharski L, Araujo A, Lucion A. (2016) Effects of sleep restriction during pregnancy on the mother and fetuses. 155 (2016) 66–76
- [21] Kızılırmak A, Timur S and Kartal B. (2012) Insomnia in Pregnancy and Factors Related to Insomnia. vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 243–263, 2000.
- [22] Chang JJ, Pien GW, Duntley SP, Macones GA. Sleep Deprivation during Pregnancy and Maternal and Fetal Outcomes: Is There a Relationship? 2010 Apr;14(2):107-14.
- [23] Rechiner C. Insomnia and sleep deficiency in pregnancy. 2015 Dec; 8(4): 168.

Appendix 1:**1- Age**

- 18
- 19
- 20
- 21
- 22
- 23
- 24 and above

2- Educational Status?

- Not Educated
- Primary school
- Middle school
- Secondary school
- University

3- Living area?

- City
- rural

4- Are you a smoker?

- No I had never smoke.
- Ex-smoker
- Yes ,Current smoker

5- Amount of tea/Coffee Consumed daily?

- One Cup
- Two Cups
- Three Cups
- 4 and more Cups

6- Number of Pregnancies?

- One
- Two
- Three
- Four and More

7- Average Sleeping hours before pregnancy?

- Less than 7 hours
- 7-8 hours
- 9
- 10 and more

8- Average sleeping hours during pregnancy?

- Less than 7 hours
- 7-8 hours
- 9
- 10 and more

9- How long it takes from u to fall asleep during pregnancy?

10- Do you take a nap during the daytime?

- Yes
- No

11- Do you have snoring during sleep?

- Yes
- No

12- Have you try to take any medication to help you to sleep during pregnancy?

- Yes
- No

13- Does Poor Sleep during pregnancy has adverse effects on the fetus/mother?

- Yes
- No

14- Does Poor Sleep during pregnancy increase the risk of premature delivery and birth?

- True
- False

15- Does Poor Sleep during pregnancy increase the risk of cesarean delivery?

- True
- False

16- Does poor sleep during pregnancy increase the risk of postpartum depression?

- True
- False

17- Does poor sleep during pregnancy increase the risk of hypertension, preeclampsia and gestational diabetes?

- True
- False

18- Women with poor sleep during pregnancy may experience longer and painful labor compared with women having sufficient sleep?

- True
- False

19- Poor sleep during pregnancy may increase the risk of Fetal intrauterine growth restriction?

- True
- False

20- Poor sleep during pregnancy can be managed with certain medications?

- True
- False